

Figure S1 Shows the laser melting simulation obtained using LIMP simulation program for both lasers.

Figure S1 Simulation of LIMP program to verify the melting depth of the laser used with respect to the laser fluence used.

Figure S2 Shows the experimental transmittance and reflectance for a sample implanted with Cr and processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser and a sample implanted with Cr and processed with Nd-YAG laser, along with their fitting calculations

Figure S2 Experimental transmittance and reflectance for a sample processed by PLM using ArF⁺ excimer laser and Nd-YAG laser and a sample implanted and subsequently processed by PLM (GaAs:Cr) using ArF⁺ excimer laser and Nd-YAG laser and fitting calculations.

Figure S3 shows the phase obtained with the lock-in during the photoresponsivity measurements. The reference sample shows a constant phase related to the expected photoresponse. The non-implanted and processed with ArF⁺ excimer and Nd-YAG lasers show a constant phase throughout the measurements. The implanted GaAs:Cr and processed with ArF⁺ excimer laser shows a constant phase above the bandgap and a shift in the phase right after the bandgap (880 nm) related to a signal below the bandgap. The implanted GaAs:Cr and processed with Nd-YAG laser shows a similar phase to the reference sample, where a noise level is seen below the bandgap.

Figure S3 As measured Lock-In phase of the photoresponse observed in our fabricated samples.